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Employed People Who Work from Home in the Italian Regions

They grew by 120% on average

Istat calculates the value of employees who work from home. The variable is defined as the percentage of employed people who have carried out their work from home in the last 4 weeks out of the total number of employed people. The data refers to the period 2018-2022 in the 20 Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of employees working from home in 2022. Lazio is in first place by value of employees working from home in 2022 with an amount of 21.1 units, followed by Lombardy with a value of 15.2 units and from Liguria with a value of 13.7 units. In the middle of the table are Tuscany with a value of 10.1 units, followed by Sardinia with a value of 10 units and Umbria with a value of 8.8 units. Sicily closes the ranking with a value of 7.3 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with a value of 6.7 units, and Puglia with a value of 6.6 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in people working from home between 2018 and 2022. Lazio is in first place by value of the percentage change in people working from home between 2018 and 2022 with an amount equal to 257.63% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 5.90 units in 2018 up to a value of 21.10 units in 2022. Lombardy follows with a variation equal to +186.79% corresponding to a variation from an amount from 5.30 units up to 15.20 units or equal to an amount of 9.90 units. Sardinia is in third place in terms of the value of employees working from home between 2018 and 2022 corresponding to a variation of 170.27% equal to a variation from an amount of 3.70 units up to a value of 10.00 units. In the middle of the table are Puglia with a variation equal to 120.005 corresponding to a variation from 3.00 units in 2018 up to a value of 6.60 units in 2022. Sicily follows with a value of 108.57% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.50 units up to 7.30 units. And finally, still in the middle of the table, there is Molise with a percentage variation equal to 105.565 corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.60 units up to a value of 7.40 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of 67.505 equal to a variation from an amount of 4.70 units up to a value of 7.40 units. Followed by Abruzzo with a variation equal to an amount of 57.45% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.70 units up to 7.40 units. And finally Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation equal to an amount of 53.62% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.90 units up to 10.60 units. On average, the value of those employed from home went from an amount of 4.67 in 2018 to a value of 10.305 in 2022 with a variation of +120.66%. However, the most significant positive change occurred in the transition between 2019 and 2020, i.e. during Covid-19. In fact, between 2019 and 2020 the value of those employed at home grew from an amount of 4.59 units up to a value of 12.515.

Employees who work from home in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022. Employees who work from home grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022. Specifically, this

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value grew in the North by amount equal to +141.82%, in the North-West for +173.58%, in the North-East for 110.71%, in the Central Italy for 175.93%, in the South for an amount of 122.86%, and in the Islands for an amount of 120.00%. However, we can note that, in all Italian macro-regions, the value of employees working from home grew in 2020 and 2021 and instead decreased slightly in 2022. Covid 19 has made a significant contribution to the growth of employees working from home. However, the end of the pandemic has led to a significant reduction in this value even if overall the number of employees working from home is higher in 2022 than the corresponding values of 2018 and 2019 in the Italian macro-regions.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data highlights the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Emilia Romagna, Liguria, Lombardy, Piedmont, Trentino Alto Adige, Lazio, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Veneto;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Molise, Basilicata, Calabria, Puglia, Marche, Abruzzo, Campania, Valle d'Aosta, Umbria, Sardinia.

Considering the average value of the clusters we can see the following ordering: $C1 > C2$. It follows that the regions of Central-Northern Italy tend to have values of people employed from home that are much higher than the values of Cluster 2. In particular, the only regions of Central-Northern Italy that are part of cluster 2 are: Valle d'Aosta and Umbria. The central-northern regions therefore have much higher numbers of employees working from home than the corresponding southern regions. This value may also be due to the presence of larger companies in the Centre-North that have employment policies capable of recognizing smartworking for their employees more efficiently.

Conclusions. The value of home workers grew significantly between 2018 and 2022. Covid 19 increased the value of home workers. However, between 2021 and 2022 the value of those employed from home decreased on average in all Italian macro-regions. In any case, there is a gap between the southern regions and the central-northern regions in terms of the number of employees working from home. This difference between southern and northern regions may also depend on the presence of a work culture which in northern regions is more oriented towards recognizing workers' rights and guaranteeing a much more efficient level of welfare than in southern regions. Finally, the fact that there are much larger companies in the northern regions compared to companies in the southern regions could have an impact on the ability of production organizations to recognize smart working for employees. Finally, in cities where the cost per square meter of rent for office buildings is very high, i.e. in Northern cities, companies could have economic-financial advantages in offering smart working to employees by reducing the cost of company rent.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are

all free version without licenses.

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References

Leogrande, A., Birardi, G., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2019). Italian Universities: Institutional Mandate and Communitarian Engagement. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 2(2), 85-110.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The smes innovation in europe. Available at SSRN 3964059.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Laureti, Lucio, Alberto Costantiello, and Angelo Leogrande. "THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT." IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics. 2021.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. Available at SSRN 4434206.

Appendix

